

Impact of Pharmaceutical Care on Clinical Outcomes in Patients with Rheumatic Heart Disease: A Six-Month Prospective Study in South Punjab

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Abstract

Background: Rheumatic Heart Disease (RHD) remains a significant public health concern in developing countries, including Pakistan. This prospective study was conducted at the Chaudhary Pervaiz Elahi Institute of Cardiology, Multan, from July to December, to assess clinical patterns and evaluate pharmaceutical care in pediatric RHD.

Objective: To analyze demographic and clinical characteristics, diagnostic findings, management practices, socioeconomic factors, and hygiene-related risk indicators among pediatric RHD patients, and to design and implement a pharmaceutical care plan to optimize therapy and follow-up.

Materials and Methods: Children aged 5–15 years presenting with recurrent Group A β -hemolytic streptococcal (GABHS) pharyngitis and diagnosed with RHD by a pediatric cardiologist-based on clinical signs, echocardiography, and the Modified Jones Criteria were consecutively enrolled and followed for at least three months. Patients with unrelated cardiac or respiratory disorders were excluded. A structured SOAP-based pharmaceutical care form was completed for each patient

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to guide individualized treatment and monitoring.

Results: A total of 134 patients were included (rural: 48; urban: 86). Most patients were 11–13 years old (rural: 40.7%; urban: 41.6%). Rural males were more affected (58.3%), while sex distribution was similar in urban patients. Fever and arthritis were the predominant symptoms. Mitral regurgitation was the most common echocardiographic finding (rural: 47.9%; urban: 52.3%). All patients received benzyl penicillin; diuretics and ACE inhibitors were commonly prescribed. Overcrowding and poor hygiene emerged as major risk factors, with most families not meeting acceptable living-condition standards.

Conclusion: Recurrent sore throat remains a major precursor to RHD in children. Improving hygiene, reducing overcrowding, and increasing awareness can significantly lower disease risk. Pharmaceutical care interventions may further enhance disease management and follow-up.

Introduction

Rheumatic Heart Disease (RHD) is caused by the long-term damage to heart muscles or heart valves by Acute Rheumatic Fever (ARF). ARF is an inflammatory disease that occurs after untreated or insufficiently treated upper respiratory tract infection like pharyngitis, caused by Group A Beta Hemolytic Streptococcus bacterium (GABHS). ARF is characterized by high grade fever, pain in joints leading to valvular damage. RHD as the sequelae of ARF is the commonest cause of heart diseases in children between the ages of 5-15 years globally. The complications of GABHS pharyngitis and delayed immune response may result in valvular regurgitation and stenosis.

The incidence of rheumatic fever and rheumatic heart disease has decreased significantly in the developed countries. However, there are still significant health problems in under developed, developing countries like Pakistan and in the indigenous population of Australia and New Zealand (Sadiq, et al:2009, Alizzi AM et al: 2010, Wilson N:2010, Remenyl, et al:2012). WHO has estimated that about 1.33 lakh deaths occur from RF/RHD annually in the south east Asia compared to 10,000 deaths in America and 30,000 deaths in Europe. (WHO, 2004)

Low socioeconomic status characterized by poverty, overcrowding, unemployment, unhygienic conditions have been associated with RHD. These risk factors have rarely been investigated in Pakistan (Rizvi, et al: 2004). Other risk factors associated with a high risk in the population include poor health care access, remoteness of the affected area from the health care facility, lack of adequate follow-up of the diseased person and lack of knowledge of ARF/RHD among health staff, patients and community. (White, et al: 2011, Carapetis, et al: 2000).

Research has proven that the probability of RHD/RF, in developing countries, can be reduced by preventive care and especially through secondary prevention. Diseases prevention is paramount than instead of providing therapies to patients after they got ill. Pharmaceutical Care also called pharmacist care play an important role in this regard. It describes Specific activities and services through which an individual pharmacist cooperates with a patient and other professionals in designing, implementing and monitoring a therapeutic plan that will produce specific therapeutic outcomes for the patient. (Helper and Strand, 1990)

In addition, it also includes assessment of patient physical and psycho-social problems. Pharmacist role is to motivate and educate patient about therapeutic regimens. He can recognize therapeutic problems by interpreting laboratory tests and should manage drug related problems such as ADR and drug-drug interactions, so he must have knowledge about community resources. He has the potential to recognize patient at risk and to apply pharmacokinetic principles for the determination of dose of prescribed drugs. Pharmacist role is to plan and implement pharmaceutical care activities in community pharmacy, ambulatory care services, home health services etc. We designed this study to investigate the prevalence of RHD among the children. The study also had two objectives. One of which was to investigate role of socioeconomic

2 rooms	3 persons
3 rooms	5 persons
4 rooms	7 persons
5 or more rooms	10 persons (additional 2 for further room)

Hygienic Conditions

Hygienic condition was determined through a questionnaire containing questions about availability of toilet facility with hand washing and without hand washing practice.

Counseling of patients and their attendants

The patients & their attendants were counseled on the following points in their mother tongue (Punjabi, Saraiki etc.) & were also provided with Urdu translation (Annex) for strict compliance.

Patient should get injection after every third week with regularity.

Get the injection on the fleshy part of the body.

Before getting injection, patient should take allergic test.

After getting injection, patient should remain under observation for some time.

Take all medicines with regularity according to Doctor or Pharmacist instructions.

Parents should not let their children to eat spicy & bitter food to avoid sore throat.

Patients should not play with dirt & if they do so, they should properly clean & wash themselves.

Patients should wash their hands after using toilet.

If patient suffers from sore throat & fever, then parents should immediately take their child to doctor.

After operation, patients should take INR (International Normalize Ratio) test every month so that proper dose of medicine can be prescribed.

Patients should avoid green leafy vegetables like spinach.

Pharmaceutical care plan development

It was developed according to SOAP format. A structured approach for questioning to collect objective information from patient was employed. To minimize the risk of missing vital information, a mnemonics SITDOWNSIR was used (Edwards & Kiska, 2004). These mnemonics stand for:

S	Site or location
I	Intensity or severity
T	Type or nature
D	Duration
O	Onset
W	With (other symptoms)
N	aNnoyed or aggravated by
R	Relieved by

All the information about every patient were gathered in a separate pharmaceutical care Performa which is given in the Annex.

Data Analysis:

All the data were collected in the form of percentage, means, standard deviation for continuous variables and student t-test were employed for comparative analysis between Urban and Rural RHD patients at 5% significant level.

Results

The results of this study have been compiled from the **Subjective** and **Objective** information of the pharmaceutical care Performa prepared by the researcher under SOAP format for individual RHD patients. Data of the two patients who died during study period is not included.

Demographic data of RHD patients

Following is the demographic data of RHD patients included in the study, who meet the inclusion criteria. Patients were divided in Rural and Urban patients. There were 48 Rural patients and 86 Urban patients, attending CPEIC, Multan.

Age, Sex, and Month wise distribution of RHD patients

Patients suffering from RHD were within 5-15 years. Age wise distribution of male and female patients belonging to both Urban and Rural dwelling is shown graphically in Figures 1-3. Overall, 58.30% rural male patients have RHD as compared to 50% male urban patients while 37.50% rural female patients have RHD as compared to 51% urban patients.

Fig: 1: Month wise distribution of RHD Urban patients (n=86) between different age groups with sex.

Mean and S.D of 5-7 years male and female Urban RHD patients is zero. Means of 8-10 years of both male and female RHD Urban patients are 1.33 and S.D of both are 1.36 and 1.21. Means of 11-13 years male and female patients are 2.83 and 3 while S.D are 2.85 and 2.38 respectively. Similarly, means of age group greater than 13 years of both sexes are 3 and 2.83 while S.D are 1.41 and 3.54 respectively.

Fig: 2: Month wise distribution of RHD Rural patients (n=48) between different age groups with sex.

Means of 5-7 years male and female rural RHD patients are 0.16 while S.D of both are 0.4. Means of 8-10 years of both male and female RHD rural patients are 0.5 and 0.66 while S.D of both are 0.83 and 0.81 respectively. Means of 11-13 years male and female patients are 1.66 and 1.83 while S.D are 1.36 and 0.98 respectively. Similarly Means of age group greater than 13 years of both sexes are 2.33 and 0.33 while S.D are 2.94 and 0.51 respectively.

Fig: 3: Comparison of Age wise distribution of Urban and Rural RHD patients.

Figure 3 shows in between 5-7 years age group, 0% rural patients while 4.16% urban patients have RHD disease. In 8-10 years, age group, 18.60% rural while 15% urban patients have RHD disease. In 11-13 years, age group, 40.69% rural while 41.60% urban patients have RHD disease While in greater than 13 years age group, 40.69% Rural while 33.33% Urban have RHD disease.

Diagnosis of RHD according to Modified Jones Criteria

Manifestations of both minor and major symptoms of RHD according to Modified Jones Criteria are given in Tables 1-3. These Tables depict information about the patients belonging to both Urban and Rural localities.

Table: 1: Month wise distribution of Symptoms of Urban RHD patients (n=86)

	Fever	Arthritis	Chorea	Others
July	2	5	0	5
August	8	8	1	8
September	18	19	0	25
October	16	21	0	27
November	14	15	0	19
December	1	3	0	2
Mean	9.83	11.83	0.16	14.67
STDEV	7.27	7.54	0.4	4.5

Table 1 shows means and S.D of fever, arthritis, chorea and others. Mean and S.D of fever is 9.83 and 7.27 respectively. Similarly for arthritis is 11.83 and 7.54, for chorea is 0.16 and 0.4 and for other symptoms are 14.67 and 4.5 respectively.

Table: 2: Month wise distribution of Symptoms of Rural RHD patients (n=48)

	Fever	Arthritis	Chorea	Others
July	2	2	0	1
August	5	5	1	3
September	10	8	0	12
October	6	18	0	17
November	2	5	0	5
December	2	4	0	4
Mean	4.5	7	0.16	7
STDEV	3.2	5.72	0.4	3.08

Table 2 shows means and S.D of fever, arthritis, chorea and others. Mean and S.D of fever is 4.5 and 3.2 respectively. Similarly for arthritis is 7 and 5.72, for chorea is 0.16 and 0.4 and for other symptoms are 7 and 3.08 respectively.

Table: 3: Comparison of Symptoms of Rural and Urban RHD patients:

Symptoms	% age of Rural	% age of Urban
Fever	56.25	68.60
Arthritis	87.50	82.50
Chorea	2.08	1.16
Others	87.50	100

Table 3 shows that 68.60% urban patients show fever as compared to 56.25% rural patients, 82.50% urban patients show arthritis as compared to 87.50% rural patients, 1.16% urban patients show chorea as compared to 2.08% rural patients. Similarly, 100% other symptoms have shown in urban patients as compared to 87.50% in rural patients.

Echocardiography of RHD patients

RHD was confirmed by detecting abnormalities in different valves caused by GABHS infection by echocardiography techniques and results are tabulated in Tables 4-6.

Table 4: Month wise distribution of Echocardiographic manifestations of Rural RHD patients (n=48)

Months	M R	AoR +MR	AoR+MR+Pulmonary HTN	AR+MR+Pulmonary HTN	AR +M R	A R	MR+Pulmonary HTN	OTHERS
July	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
August	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	1
September	4	1	3	0	0	1	2	3
October	9	1	0	2	1	0	1	4
November	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
December	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
Mean	3.83	0.66	0.5	0.5	0.33	0.33	0.5	1.33
STDEV	2.71	0.81	1.22	0.83	0.51	0.51	0.83	1.75

Table 4 shows means and S.D of different echocardiographic manifestations of rural RHD patients. Mean and S.D of MR is 3.83 and 2.71, AoR + MR 0.66 and 0.81, AoR + MR+ Pulmonary HTN 0.5 and 1.22, AR+ MR+ Pulmonary HTN 0.5 and 0.83, AR + MR 0.33 and 0.51, AR 0.33 and 0.51, MR + Pulmonary HTN 0.5 and 0.83 while others are 1.33 and 1.75.

Table: 5: Month wise distribution of Echocardiographic manifestations of Urban RHD patients (n=86)

Months	M R	AoR+ MR	AoR+MR+Pulmonary HTN	AR+MR+Pulmonary HTN	AR+ MR	A R	MR+Pulmonary HTN	OTHERS
July	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
August	4	3	0	0	2	0	2	2
September	12	3	1	1	2	0	1	2
October	18	1	1	0	3	0	6	3
November	4	1	0	0	3	0	3	0
December	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Mean	7.5	1.33	0.33	0.16	1.83	0	2	1.16
STDEV	6.18	1.36	0.51	0.4	1.16	1.16	2.28	1.32

Table 5 shows means and S.D of different echocardiographic manifestations. Mean and S.D of MR is 7.5 and 6.18, AoR + MR 1.33 and 1.36, AoR + MR+ Pulmonary HTN 0.33 and 0.51, AR+ MR+ Pulmonary HTN 0.16 and 0.4, AR + MR 1.83 and 1.16, AR 0 and 1.16, MR + Pulmonary HTN 2 and 2.28 while others are 1.16 and 1.32.

Table: 6: Comparison of Echocardiographic manifestations between Rural and Urban RHD patients:

Echocardiographic manifestation	M R	AoR+ MR	AoR+MR+Pulmonary HTN	AR+MR+Pulmonary HTN	AR +M R	A R	MR+Pulmonary HTN	OTHERS
% age of Rural	47.91	8.33	6.25	6.25	4.16	4.16	6.25	16.66
%age of Urban	52.32	9.3	2.32	1.16	12.79	0	13.95	8.13

Table 6 shows comparison of echocardiographic manifestations between rural and urban RHD patients. 47.91% rural patients show diagnosis of MR as compared to 52.32% in urban patients. Similarly, AoR + MR in 8.33% rural as compared to 9.3% urban patients, AoR + MR + Pulmonary HTN in 6.25% rural as compared to 2.32% urban patients, AR + MR + Pulmonary HTN in 6.25% rural as compared to 1.16% urban patients, AR + MR in 4.16% rural as compared to 12.79% urban patients, AR in 4.16% rural as compared to 0% in urban patients, MR + Pulmonary HTN in 6.25% rural as compared to 13.95% urban Patients and others in 16.66% rural as compared

to 8.13% urban patients. In both the cases, results show, MR is dominant which is consistent with other studies in Asian countries. (Sriharibabu et al: 2013, Crapetis: 2008)

Treatment of RHD patients

All the drugs prescribed by the pead cardiologist and dispensed by hospital pharmacist along with proper counseling, are given in Tables 7-9.

Table 7: Month wise distribution of Drugs prescribed to Urban RHD patients (n=86)

Months	Benzyl Peni	Cardiac glycc	ACEI	Diuretics	Beta-bloc	Anti-platele	Others
July	5	4	4	4	0	1	0
August	9	8	10	10	0	2	4
September	26	16	23	24	3	4	16
October	27	19	20	24	4	3	15
November	15	11	13	13	0	1	5
December	4	2	0	3	0	2	2
Mean	14.33	10	11.66	13	1.16	2.16	7.33
STDEV	10.19	6.66	8.91	9.29	1.83	1.16	6.81

Table 7 shows means and S.D of drugs prescribed to Urban RHD patients. Mean and S.D of Benzyl Penicillin is 14.33 and 10.19, cardiac glycosides 10 and 6.66, ACE 11.66 and 8.91, Diuretics 13 and 9.29, Beta-blockers 1.16 and 1.83, anti-platelet 2.16 and 1.16 while others have 7.33 and 6.81 respectively.

Table 8: Month wise distribution of Drugs prescribed to Rural RHD patients (n=48)

Months	Benzyl Peni	Cardiac glycc	ACEI	Diuretics	Beta-blocke	Anti-plate	Others
July	3	1	1	2	1	1	1
August	5	2	2	4	1	1	3
September	12	10	7	10	0	0	1
October	19	13	17	18	2	2	6
November	5	1	3	4	0	1	0
December	4	4	4	4	0	0	1
Mean	8	5.16	5.66	7	0.66	0.83	2
STDEV	6.26	5.11	5.92	6.03	0.81	0.75	2.19

Table 8 shows means and S.D of drugs prescribed to Rural RHD patients. Mean and S.D of Benzyl Penicillin is 8 and 6.26, cardiac glycosides 5.16 and 5.11, ACE 5.66 and 5.92, Diuretics 7 and 6.03, Beta-blockers 0.66 and 0.81, anti-platelet 0.83 and 0.75 while others have 2 and 2.19 respectively.

Table 9: Comparison of Drugs prescribed between Rural and Urban patients

Drugs	% age of Rural	% age of Urban
Benzyl Penicillin	100	100
Cardiac glycosides	64.5	69.7
ACE Inhibitors	70.8	81.3
Diuretics	87.5	90.6
Beta-blockers	8.3	8.13
Anti-platelet	10.4	15.1
Others	25	48.8

Table 9 shows that Benzyl Penicillin is prescribed 100% to both urban and rural patients. Cardiac glycosides is prescribed 69.7% to Urban and 64.5% to rural patients, ACE Inhibitors to 81.3% urban as compared to 70.8% rural, Diuretics to 90.6% urban as compared to 87.5% rural, Beta-blockers to 8.13% urban as compared to 8.3% rural, anti-platelet to 15.1% urban as compared to 10.4% rural patients. Similarly, other drugs are prescribed 48.8% to urban as compared to 25% to rural patients.

Socioeconomic and Environmental factors of RHD

Various Socioeconomic factors considered responsible for occurrence of RHD in children of the community. The information gathered on the Performa from the individual patients are shown graphically in Figure 4-6 and some data tabulated in Table 10.

Fig 4: Dwelling of RHD patients.

Figure 4 shows means and S.D of dwelling of urban RHD patients as compared to rural RHD patients, which are 8.6 and 7.01 respectively as compared to 4.8 and 3.99 respectively.

Fig 5: Degree of overcrowding of RHD patients.

Figure 5 shows degree of overcrowding of rural and urban patients. Here is the mean and S.D of degree of overcrowding of urban patients is 10.75 and 8.04 respectively. Similarly, for rural patients 6 and 4.37 respectively

Fig 6: Comparison of Hygienic conditions between Urban and Rural RHD patients.

Figure 6 shows the comparison of hygienic conditions between urban and rural RHD patients. Toilet facility is available more to rural patients (62.5%) as compared to urban patients (56.97%).

Table 10: Comparison of Overcrowding Acceptance Criteria between Rural and Urban cohabitants

	Rural cohabitants	Urban cohabitants
Cohabitants fulfill Criteria	16.60%	10.40%
Cohabitants do not fulfill Criteria	83.30%	89.50%

Table 10 shows the comparison of Overcrowding Acceptance Criteria between the rural and urban cohabitants. Urban cohabitants (89.5%) that do not fulfill acceptance criteria are more as compared to rural Cohabitants (83.3%). Similarly, rural cohabitants (16.6%) that fulfill criteria are more than urban cohabitants (10.4%).

Discussion

GABHS Infection of upper respiratory tract, especially pharynx is one of the most common infectious diseases which are responsible for many deaths in developing and underdeveloped countries. RHD is one of the streptococcal infectious diseases and this prospective study was carried out to investigate the diagnosis, prevalence, treatment and socioeconomic and environmental factors of RHD. In this study, RHD prevalence rates are slightly higher among male patients (52.2%) as compared to female patients (47.7%). This observation is contrary to many other studies both in Pakistan and India (Sriharibabu, et al: 2013, Padmavati: 2001, Rizvi: 2004). RF/RHD more frequent among children and adolescents between 5 and 15 years of age as is indicated in this study. However, the prevalence of this disease is uncommon in children under 4 years of age and exceedingly rare under the age of 2 (Orun, et al: 2012). It is considered to be the leading cause of the valvar diseases in children and adolescents (Lee, et al: 2010, Ozer, et al: 2005).

For the diagnosis of RHD, typical presentations like high grade fever, red Pharynx may be characteristics symptoms of GABHS Infection but it is impossible to make a definitive diagnosis without laboratory testing (like ASO titre). Furthermore, echocardiography screening to detect any lesion in heart valves is needed. It has been

shown (Marijon, et al: 2007, Remenyl, et al: 2012) that by using echocardiography technique approximately ten times greater valvar lesions have been detected as compared to auscultation technique.

Results of this study show that long-acting Benzyl Penicillin 1.2 million IU by IM route at 3-4 weeks interval has been prescribed to all the patients whether belonging to urban or rural areas. In accordance with WHO guidelines (WHO 2004, Manyemba and Mayosi: 2004) both for Primary and Secondary Prevention of ARF/RHD. Use of Penicillin as a secondary prophylaxis is considered most cost effective and safe in persistent worsening RHD and its sequela but there are many issues that need to be resolved. These include dosage interval of injectable Penicillin, length of prophylaxis and fatal allergic reactions (2 of our patients have died during study period due to anaphylactic shock of Penicillin) (Spinetto, et al: 2011, Lue, et al: 1996). Regarding length of prophylactic use of Penicillin in different periods have been recommended. The most common criteria for finishing of Penicillin injections have been recommended for patients with no or mild valvar lesion up to 10 years or up to 21 years of age and for patients without valvar disease for 5 years or at least up to the age of 18 years (Spinetto, et al: 2011).

In addition to use of Penicillin both for Primary and Secondary Prevention of RHD, other drugs like Cardiac glycosides, ACE Inhibitors, Diuretics, Beta-blocker and anti-platelets (Table 18) were also prescribed to treat RHD complications. Mitral Valve abnormalities particularly MS is considered responsible for atrial fibrillation. Other complications due to different valves abnormalities include Congestive Heart Failure, Pulmonary HTN, Infected Carditis (Carapetis: 2008, Lee, et al: 2009).

The comparison of the Socioeconomic Factors of patients shows that patients came from the low socioeconomic communities of Pakistan and overcrowding is the main socioeconomic factor among RHD patients in Pakistan. In this prospective study, more than 11 or 12 cohabitants lived in house of one or two rooms that is due to the poor sanitary and hygienic conditions. Total 87.3% RHD patients including 89.5% Urban patients and 83.3% Rural patients (Table 22) did not fulfill the acceptance criteria of the overcrowding. Watkins and Quinn: 1948 and Chagani and Aziz: 2003 favors this observation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

On the basis of this study, it is concluded and recommended that:

RHD is caused by the Streptococcal infection that is spread in 5-15 years children due to the sore throat. This necessitates the effective measure regarding prevention and treatment of this disease in hospitals. Parents are advised to stop their children from playing with dirt and are advised to wash hands after using toilet to prevent the Streptococcal infection and they are also advised to provide the toilet facilities in their homes.

Patient and attendants counseling is highly recommended regarding healthy life style, proper hygienic conditions and regular follow-up; moreover, effective treatment therapy also needs to be addressed properly by the Health Care Providers and Pharmacists.

There is increased risk of RHD due to the overcrowding in Pakistan, so it is further advised that in every single room not more than two individuals be made to stay.

It is recommended that Pharmacist prepare an effective Pharmaceutical Care Plan regarding RHD patients which may include counseling the patients and their attendants about the Penicillin allergic reactions, drug interactions and adverse drug reactions.

It is further recommended that Community Pharmacists led awareness programme be initiated to educate parents and patients about possible complications of sore throat and convince the physician to treat Pharyngitis with Penicillin.

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ANNEXURES

Performa# 1

Pharmaceutical care plan for Rheumatic heart disease patients:

An individual dedicated plan to address the drug related problems for RHD patients under SOAP format.

Subjective Information:

Entry # _____ CPEIC Reg # _____ Date: _____
____/____/_____
Patient's Name: _____
Father's Name: _____ Age/Sex: _____ No.of cohabitants: _____
No. of Rooms: _____ Income/month: _____ House
Area _____
Address: _____ Cell # _____
History of present/past illness: _____
Family history (related to the disease) _____
Allergies: _____
Medication
history: _____

Objective Information: (According to mnemonics SITDOWN SIR)

Symptoms:

Sore throat: Yes/No, if yes: when and for how long? _____

Joint pain/Swelling: Yes/No, if yes: Which Joint? _____

Fever: Yes/No, if yes: High grade/Low grade. _____

Abnormal movement/Behavior: Yes/No SOB/Palpitation: Yes/No
Aggravated _____ by:

Relieved _____ by:

Laboratory Examination:

Hb _____ ESR _____

ASO Titer _____ CRP _____

Echo _____ **Cardiography:** _____

Conclusion: _____

Final _____ Diagnosis: _____

Prescribed Drugs:

Drug	Dose	Dosage form	Rout of Administration	Frequency

Assessment by Pharmacist: This part of SOAP profile covers therapeutic objectives/goals, drug-related problems and brief description of therapeutic alternatives.

If patient shows hypersensitivity to Penicillin, then erythromycin can be given to patient as a therapeutic alternative.

Pharmaceutical Care Plan:

It includes a plan for improvement of signs/symptoms, early detection of drug-related problems and suggestions for therapeutic alternatives and therapeutic drug monitoring.

The usual drug-related problems are:

Contra-Indications: _____**Drug-Drug Interactions:**

Drug-Drug Interaction	Onset	Severity	Documentation	Significance level	Effects	Management

Adverse Drug Reactions: This portion includes suggestion for prevention of some and early detection of other ADR's and reporting of any existed ADR,s due to the prescribed drugs and submission of Yellow Card to the relevant authority.

Patient Counseling:

1. Patient should get injection after every third week with regularity.
2. Get the injection on the fleshy part of the body.
3. Before getting injection, patient should take allergic test.
4. After getting injection, patient should remain under observation for sometime.
5. Take all medicines with regularity according to Doctor or Pharmacist instructions.
6. Parents should not let their children to eat spicy and bitter food to avoid sore throat.
7. Patients should not play with dirt and if they do so, they should properly clean and wash themselves.

8. Patients should wash their hands after using toilet.
9. If patient suffers from sore throat and fever, then parents should immediately take their child to Doctor.
10. After operation, patients should take INR (International Normalize Ratio) test every month so that proper dose of medicine can be prescribed.
11. Patients should avoid green leafy vegetables like spinach.

Follow-up Plan:

Patients were said to do visit to the hospital every month and regularly get injection every month. Patients should follow the prescription regularly.